

Potential of rice and potato inter/relay cropping system with sugarcane

G.P. Singh and S.N. Singh, Uttar Pradesh Council of Sugarcane Research, Shahjahanpur 242001, Uttar Pradesh, India

The planting spindle bud culture method was developed to exploit productivity and profitability per unit area. The method uses inter/relay cropping of rice and potato with sugarcane, and two sugarcane cuttings from the same piece of land in 1 1/2 yr. With this, the profitability of the system can be further improved by growing wheat as an intercrop after the cane's second cutting in Nov-Dec.

After field preparation, 1-mo-old plantlets of sugarcane developed by the spindle bud culture technique were transplanted in rows at a distance of 90 cm on 20 Jun. Thereafter, five rows of rice (Saket 4) were transplanted 18 cm apart (normal spacing is 20 cm) in interrow spaces of sugarcane after flooding, followed by semipuddling by a plow. The rice crop, with a plant population of 100% on a per unit area basis, was harvested during the second half of Oct. After that, one row of potato

was sown by the ridge method after field preparation, maintaining 50% of the plant population at a row-to-row distance of 45 cm. Potato tubers were harvested in the first half of Feb and yield was recorded.

The sugarcane crop planted on 20 Jun formed sparse canopies. The mature canes (first crop cutting) were harvested during the last week of Mar. Thereafter, stubbles along with water shoots and late-formed tillers were left to grow from Apr onward. Final harvesting was done in Nov and cane yield and quality characters were recorded. A split-plot statistical design was used, with planting technique as the main plot and inter/relay cropping system as the subplot.

The nutrient needs of all three crops were met separately based on standard recommendations. The field was fertilized with 180 kg N ha⁻¹ for sugarcane, and 120-60-60 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for rice and potato. In sugarcane, a basal dose of 1/4 N was applied at transplanting and the remaining 3/4 dose in four equal splits (two top-dressed after harvesting of rice and potato and the remaining two top-dressed after harvesting of mature canes after Mar at tillering). In addition,

two foliar sprays of urea at 10% were given to the second crop of sugarcane in Jul. In rice and potato, the above nutrient doses were given based on the recommended application method.

Moreover, five manual hoeings/weedings were done in the interrow spaces of sugarcane to allow it to develop a full canopy.

The mean yield of transplanted rice intercropped with sugarcane was 4.3 t ha⁻¹, 17.4% more than that of direct-seeded rice (see table). Rice yield in this system was not affected adversely to a large extent due to sparse canopy and less tillering of sugarcane brought about by decreasing temperature, as shown by the sugarcane yield in the first cutting. But yield of intercropped cane averaged 18.2% less than that of sugarcane alone. Potato intercropped with transplanted sugarcane plantlets yielded more because of sufficient space for cultural operations. The yield of sugarcane using transplanted plantlets was 35% higher than the standard method, which reduced germination.

In the second cutting, sugarcane yield was much higher under inter/relay cropping than in sole cane. This is due to the dense canopy and greater

Production potentials of rice and potato inter/relay cropping system with sugarcane.^a

Treatment	Rice yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Potato yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield of sugarcane (t ha ⁻¹)			Commercial cane sugar (%)			Cost of cultivation (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Gross return (Rs ha ⁻¹) ^b	Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)
			First cutting	Second cutting	Total	First cutting	Second cutting	Mean			
T1: Transplanting of sugarcane plantlets alone	–	–	43.4	89.2	132.6	10.8	11.0	10.9	32,631	92,827	60,196
T2: Transplanting of plantlets + rice (transplanted) – potato	4.2	16.5	37.2	101.5	138.7	10.7	10.7	10.7	50,107	147,922	97,815
T3: Transplanting of plantlets + rice (broadcast) – potato	3.5	15.4	36.3	99.4	135.8	10.4	10.7	10.6	49,486	140,552	91,066
T4: Setts ^c planting of sugarcane alone	–	–	29.7	74.1	103.9	10.5	10.3	10.4	32,811	72,709	39,898
T5: Setts planting + rice (transplanted) – potato	4.4	14.2	23.7	89.6	113.4	10.3	10.0	10.2	50,287	125,651	75,364
T6: Setts planting + rice (broadcast) – potato	3.7	13.0	22.5	86.8	109.3	10.4	10.7	10.6	49,690	117,516	67,826

^aNet plot size used : 8 × 4.5 = 36.0 m². ^bPrevailing market prices: Sugarcane, Rs70 q⁻¹, Rice, Rs360 q⁻¹, Potato, Rs215 q⁻¹. ^cA sett is a mature cane cut into pieces of 2-3 internodes/nodes (eyes) and used for planting as a seed material.

number of cane plants caused by favorable temperature in April as well as by the residual effect of potato on cane plants. The commercial cane sugar (CCS) percentage in cane was more or less identical under different cropping

systems. Overall performance for yield and economic returns of rice, potato, and sugarcane were higher under the inter/relay cropping system of sugarcane + rice-potato (preferably with

transplanted plantlets) than under the sole cane crop. This method can be successfully adopted by small and marginal farmers after the May harvest of late-sown wheat. ■

Farm machinery

Rice-cum-green manure culture with modified drum seeder under lowland condition

P. Rajendran, A. Tajuddin, and C. Ramaswami, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We initially investigated *Sesbania aculeata* as an intercrop in wet-seeded rice. Compared with rice alone, rice intercropped with green manure (GM) had a yield advantage when GM was incorporated at about 35-40 cm height. Mean height of the rice crop was 32 cm. Further work is required, however, to find cheaper ways of incorporating GM and weeding to reduce cultivation costs.

A modified seeder was developed based on the IRRI drum seeder design (Fig. 1). The seeder was field-tested in a 0.03-ha unreplicated plot in 1998. It has two wheels and sows rice and GM in alternate rows 12.5 cm apart. The seeder width is 0.75 m. The walking speed is around 1.5 km h⁻¹. Including time loss for unhooking and hooking the handle after each pass, two men can cover 0.54 ha d⁻¹. The advantages of the seeder are shown in Table 1.

The low seeding rate of GM (20 kg ha⁻¹) was due to seed availability.

The GM intercrop was trampled both manually and by using the IRRI single-row conoweeder at 36 DAS (Fig. 2). Table 2 shows the benefits of the technology.

This trial indicated the possibility of intercropping rice with GM as a potentially useful technology. Fine-tuning of the intercropping technology considering rice duration, cultivation season, and location is the focus of future research. ■

Table 1. Advantages of the seeder.

	Modified seeder for rice + GM intercropping	Transplanting rice
Duration, wet biomass addition, seeding rate of GM	36 d, 7 t ha ⁻¹ , and 20 kg ha ⁻¹ , respectively	Advantage of dual cropping does not exist
Green manure height and number of nodules plant ⁻¹	40 cm and 35, respectively	-
Rice establishment charges over same preparatory cultivation	\$15 ha ⁻¹ ^a	\$100 ha ⁻¹

^aIncludes additional cost for proper leveling.

Table 2. Benefits of using the modified seeder.

	Trampling-cum-weeding by IRRI single-row conoweeder	Manual trampling
Labor requirement (man-days)	18 ha ⁻¹	54 ha ⁻¹
Cost involved ha ⁻¹	US\$14	US\$42
Additional benefit compared with no intercrop	Weeds are buried completely, thereby adding more organic matter.	

1. A modified IRRI drum seeder. (Net weight = 17 kg, wheel diameter = 60 cm, drum diameter = 20 cm).